

Tashkent State transport University
Mamurova Feruza Islamovna
Obutjonova Durdona Omonjon kizi
Temirova Madina Tohir kizi

Annotation: this article spoke about the importance of the work of Maqsud Shaykhzoda in the education of young people, such qualities as courage, fairness, thoughtful thinking, popularism, expressed in the image of the heroes of the work in Uzbek literature.

Keywords: creativity, courage, fairness, thoughtful thought, popularism, literary critic

The work is politically charged that the past is idealized. The confiscated items included a manuscript of the drama. After the author was acquitted and returned, certain organizations did not return the manuscript on the pretext that it was “lost”. The sheikhzoda was forced to search for him for several years, and finally manages to find a copy of him from the former soufflés of the theater. But even then the text of the work will not be published. Look at the play of fate, the author turned a blind eye from the universe, not seeing that this work was published.

The work of Maqsud Shaykhzoda is so interesting that he was a versatile talent in Shaykhzoda, who had a very interesting activity not only in one direction, but in different directions. Along with poems and epics, he also creates dramas with a very high artistic capacity. Not counting the drama “Beruniy”, which shaykhzoda entered into writing at the end of his life, but did not finish, his dramas “Jaloliddin Mangubardi” and “Mirzo Ulugbek” have already become the artistic property of our people. Shaykhzoda's tragedy “Jaloliddin Manguberdi” (1944), written during the years of World War II, historically accurately and insults the martial courage of the last Khwarezmian King, who fought against the Mongol conquerors for the freedom and independence of his land. Oybek and Ghafur Ghulam gave the work a high assessment at the time, saying: “the true meaning of the historical process, its inner meaning” was revealed. Until 1946, some excerpts from the drama” Jaloliddin Manguberdi “had been printed in the” Armughan ” collection. For 43 years after that, the work was not mentioned and did not see the face of the world. The work was imprisoned in the sheikhdom shortly after it was taken from the stage.

2-TOM, 1-SON

The full text of "Jaloliddin Manguberdi" was first printed and released in Baku in the two-volume edition of Shaykhzoda in Azerbaijani. It was not until 1988 that Jaloliddin Manguberdi was first published in full print by an Uzbek-language writer in his book "The Immortal World". The sharpness of shaykhzoda's mind of writing and creativity is once again proven. Another great contribution of Maqsd Shaikhzoda to Uzbek literature is the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek". The tragedy is written in 1964, the same year the work is put on the stage of the Hamza Theater, on the basis of which a motion picture is later created. As a literary critic and critic, shaikhzade also shook an effective pen, became a famous poet of Uzbek folk oral creativity, works such as "Alpomish", "sugar with sugar", Babur, Muqimiy, Furqat, Oybek, Ghafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjon, Nizami Ganjaviy of world literature, Sh.Rustaveli, A.S.Pushkin, N.A.Nekrasov, A.N.Ostrovsky, T.G.Shevchenko, A.P.Like Chekhov, he eats works dedicated to his manifestations. And as an pedagogical scientist and poet, talaygina makes a worthy contribution to the maturation of the generation of poets, literary scholars and critics.

Maqsd Shaykhzadeh as the owner of high knowledge, his entire creation was filled with a deep political publicistic spirit. His poetic, dramatic works are in harmony with the times, no matter what theme they are devoted to. That is why it is not accidental that the creator serves in the direct publicistic genre of this type. His publicistic articles and speeches, which have an excellent artistic genre, are a bright badge from the content and variety of this talented adib creativity. The talented poet was also a skilled translator. He serves greatly in translating the works of classical poets of world literature into Uzbek. In particular, Shakespeare's "Hamlet" and "Romeo and Juliet" are staged on the stage of Uzbek drama theaters in the translation of the Sheikhzoda. The growth of the poet's skill was also due to the fact that he studied the classical works of World Literature in great love, masterfully mastering their rich artistic experience. He had also thoroughly studied his fatherland literature - the heritage of Oriental poetry-with an excellent knowledge of Western European and Russian literature. Maqsd Shaykhzoda is imprisoned completely unreasonably at the beginning of the 50s and exiled for 25 years. After Stalin's death, the case of those who were unjustly imprisoned with slander was re-seen. Thus, in 1955, Shaykhzoda, among many of our dedicated intellectuals, was acquitted. But as a result of 5 years of prison suffering, the poet's health had deteriorated greatly. Nevertheless, he was forced to live on the top floor of a tall house for 10 years until the end of his life. Even in such harsh conditions and illness, sira nolimay from her life did not stop creating for the rest of her life. No matter how many sorrowful days have passed from the beginning, it has not been oppressed at all. His faith, his view of the world, Theran is described in the above

2-TOM, 1-SON

verses. He never lived in alamzada. On the contrary, he did not say anything, nowhere about those who betrayed him, subjected him to suffering, serious illnesses. True to his human qualities, shaykhzoda always lived on a rise with benevolence and high qualities.

Because he had no few genuine, loyal friends either. These included Oybek, Ghafur Ghulam, Hamid Olimjan, Komil Yashin, Mirtemir, Shukur Burkhan. Translation Mukhim played a role in the expansion of the sphere of literary knowledge of the sheikhzoda, the enrichment of his work with the artistic experience of classical world writers. It Is Located At.Rustaveli's epic" The paxlavon with the tiger skin covered", U.Shakespeare's sonnets, a.S.Poems by Pushkin, epic" The Copper rider", tragedy" Mozart and Salieri", M.Yu.Lermontov's poems and the epic "prisoner of the Caucasus" also translated with great skill into Uzbek The Works of Nizami, Fuzuli, Mirza Fatali Okhundov, Ezop, Aeschylus, Goethe, Byron, Mayakovsky, Nozim Hikmat and some other writers. The Hall of study named after writer, literary playwright, master of translation, great educator, linguist and literary critic Maqsud Shaykhzadeh and the exposition was organized in an incredibly delicate taste and in essence in harmony with the great art of Dargasiyu, great historical figures such as Jalaliddin Manguberd. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 24, 1998 "on the celebration of the 800th anniversary of the birth of Jalaliddin Manguberdi", announced by the signature of our President Islam Karimov, which adequately addressed the history of our people, including the fate and struggle of Jalaliddin Manguberdi, defended the truth, also reaffirms. The poet dies of illness on February 19, 1967. After his death, a six-volume "works" will be published. During the years of independence, the work of the late Maqsud Shaikhzoda and his services found real value.

LITERATURE USED:

1. Mamurova, F. I. (2021, May). ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN MAKSUD SHEIKHZADE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 176-178).
2. Mamurova, F. I., & ugli Abdubahabov, A. A. (2023). TWO FOLK POETS. "TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE", 1(3), 23-30.
3. Islomovna, M. F., & Abduvoxob o'g'li, A. A. (2023, January). Maqsud Shayxzodaning Hayoti Va Ijodi. In *Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences (USA)* (pp. 19-20).
4. Mamurova, F. (2023). MAQSUD SHAYXZODANING ADABIY MEROSI. *Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана*, 1(11), 9-11.
5. Olimov, S. S., & Mamurova, D. I. (2022). Directions For Improving Teaching Methods. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 9671-9678.

2-TOM, 1-SON

6. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Graphic Information Processing Technology and its Importance //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2021. – T. 10. – C. 1-4.
7. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Information Technology in Education //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 17-22.
8. Khodjayeva N. S., Mamurova D. I., Nafisa A. Importance in pedagogical techniques and educational activity //International Engineering Journal For Research & Development. – 2020. – T. 5. – C. 5-5.
9. Islomovna M. F. et al. DESIGNING THE METHODOICAL SYSTEM OF THE TEACHING PROCESS OF COMPUTER GRAPHICS FOR THE SPECIALTY OF ENGINEER-BUILDER //Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business & Government. – 2021. – T. 27. – №. 4.
10. Xodjayeva N. S. et al. KOMPYUTER GRAFIKASI NING INFORMATSION JAMIYATDAGI AHAMIYATI, RO'LI VA O'RNI //ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI. – 2022. – T. 1. – C. 74-77.
11. Saidovna, Turdieva Nigora. "Raising the attitude of primary school students to education as a value." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 10.10 (2020): 506-510.
12. Saidovna T. N. Pedagogical ethics and pedagogical tact //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 3. – C. 305-310.
13. Saidovna T. N. The Concept of the Teacher's Pedagogical Technique //European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science. – 2022. – T. 4. – C. 877-883.

